

Spectrophotometric Methods for the Determination of Carbaryl, Carbofuran and Baygon in Commercial Formulations

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Manuscript received 4 January 1996, revised 30 October 1996, accepted 8 November 1996

Carbaryl (1-naphthyl-*N*-methyl carbamate), carbofuran (2,3-dihydro-2, 2-dimethyl-7-benzofuranyl-*N*-methyl carbamate) and baygon (2-isopropoxyphenyl-*N*-methyl carbamate) belong to an important group of insecticides based on carbamate group. In view of their wide applications, convenient and reliable methods for their analysis are highly desirable. The method¹ commonly employed for their analysis consists in hydrolysing them in presence of an alkali and measuring the liberated amine acidimetrically. This method, besides requiring a special apparatus for saponification-evolution of amine, is time-consuming and demands strict experimental control. Any impurity that yields volatile base in formulations containing acidic/basic diluents, interferes in the method. This, therefore, creates a need for simple, accurate and rapid method.

Carbaryl, carbofuran and baygon hydrolyse in the presence of an alkali to give phenolic compounds and the latter react with lead(IV) acetate in glacial acetic acid (1 : 2 molar ratio) to form soluble bright yellow products showing maximum absorbances at 358, 375 and 400 nm respectively. This constitutes the basis of spectrophotometric methods (both colorimetric and photometric titrimetric) for the determination of the above insecticides.

Results and Discussion

The Beer's law for carbaryl, carbofuran and baygon is followed upto 20, 10 and 12 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the sample solution respectively. The molar absorptivities are 1.41×10^3 , 1.66×10^3 and $1.33 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The maximum relative standard deviations (RSD's) calculated from the pooled data of all the runs made with 2 and 10 μg of carbaryl, carbofuran and baygon are 0.75, 0.60 and 0.80% respectively. The colorimetric method when applied to the analysis of commercial formulations of above insecticides for their active ingredient contents, gave recoveries corresponding to 99.6, 98.3 and 99.0% of the nominal content with RSD values of 0.6, 0.7 and 0.5% respectively (Table 1). With photometric titrations, these insecticides in the range 4–20 μg could be determined with maximum RSD's of 0.70, 0.63 and 0.75% respectively. For commercial formulaions, these titrations gave recoveries corresponding to 99.8, 99.6 and 99.5% respectively, of nominal content with RSD values of 0.5, 0.5 and 0.4% respectively (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DIRECT COLORIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CARBARYL, CARBOFURAN AND BAYGON*

Insecticide	Amount found (μg) ^a	Amount found (μg) ^b
Carbaryl	2.01 (0.015)	10.08 (0.072)
Carbofuran	1.98 (0.012)	9.92 (0.058)
Baygon	2.02 (0.016)	9.94 (0.048)

*Values are mean of five determinations with standard deviation (\pm) in parenthesis. ^aAmount taken = 2.0 μg . ^bAmount taken = 10.0 μg .

The results indicate that each molecule of naphthol, carbofuran-phenol and *o*-isopropoxyphenol (hydrolysis products of carbaryl, carbofuran and baygon, respectively) consumes two moles of lead(IV) acetate (Scheme 1).

The above courses of oxidation are supported by the following observations : (i) that phenolic compounds on oxidation yields quinones, is well-known², (ii) compounds IV, V and VI are yellow compounds, a colour characteristic of quinones³, and (iii) like quinones, IV, V and VI also show oxidising behaviour.

When any of the above insecticides, after hydrolysis, is reacted with a stoichiometric amount of lead(IV) acetate and the resulting solution mixed with potassium iodide, iodine is liberated quantitatively.

Experimental

Glacial acetic acid (AnalaR) was refluxed with a little KMnO_4 for 2 h and the fraction distilled at 118° was used. A 0.05 N lead(IV) acetate solution in glacial acetic acid was prepared and standardised iodometrically. Carbaryl, carbofuran and baygon insecticides (Environmental Protection Agency, U.S.A.) were used. All other chemicals were of guaranteed quality.

A Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer and a Bausch and Lomb (Spectronic-20D) spectrophotometer were used.

Direct colorimetric procedure : To each aliquot (0.2–2.0 ml) of the solutions of each insecticide in dimethylformamide, was added NaOH solution (1 ml; 0.1 N in ethanol) and kept for 2 min. It was mixed with lead(IV) acetate (1 ml; 0.01 M) and the volume made up to 5 ml with glacial acetic acid. The absorbance of the yellow solution was measured at 355 nm (for carbaryl), 375 nm (for carbofuran) and 400 nm (for baygon) against a reagent blank. The results of analysis are given in Table 1.

A single large sample of each insecticide formulation was weighed, shaken with dimethylformamide and filtered. The residue, if any, was washed two to three times with dimethylformamide. The filtrate and washings were diluted to a known volume with the same solvent. Aliquots were then taken and processed for analysis in the manner as described above. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF SOME COMMERCIAL FORMULATIONS OF CARBARYL, CARBOFURAN AND BAYGON*

Insecticide formulation	Active ingredient (%)	Active ingredient found (%)**		
		by different methods		
		D.C.	P.T.	R.M.
Carbaryl	50	49.8 (0.6)	49.9 (0.5)	49.5 (0.8)
Carbofuran	75	74.5 (0.7)	74.7 (0.5)	74.4 (0.8)
Baygon	2	1.98 (0.5)	1.99 (0.4)	1.98 (0.7)

*Values are mean of five determinations with standard deviation (\pm) in parenthesis.
 **D.C. = Direct colorimetric method; P. T. = photometric titration method; R.M. = reported method (Ref. 1).

Photometric titration procedure : Aliquots of solutions in dimethylformamide of each pure compound were mixed with NaOH solution (0.1 ml; 0.1 N in ethanol) and each solution kept for 2 min. The volume of each solution was made up to 5 ml with glacial acetic acid. The titration was commenced by adding lead(IV) acetate in small increments and the absorbance was measured at 355 nm (for carbaryl), 375 nm (for carbofuran) and 400 nm (for baygon). Dilution corrections were applied in each case and a plot of absorbance versus ml of the titrant was made and the best straight lines drawn between the points taken well before and after the equivalence point. The intersection of linear segments was taken as the end-point in each case. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PHOTOMETRIC TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CARBARYL, CARBOFURAN AND BAYGON*

Insecticide	Amount found (μg) ^a	Amount found (μg) ^b
Carbaryl	3.97 (0.028)	20.10 (0.092)
Carbofuran	4.04 (0.025)	19.88 (0.088)
Baygon	3.96 (0.030)	19.85 (0.090)

*Values are mean of five determinations with standard deviation (\pm) in parenthesis. ^aAmount taken = 4 μg . ^bAmount taken = 20 μg .

Aliquots of extracts in dimethylformamide of formulations containing carbaryl, carbofuran and baygon were taken and processed for analysis in the same manner as described above for pure compounds. The results are given in Table 2.

References

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